

INDEX OF LEAF SURFACE AREA OF POTATO UNDER DIFFERENT FERTILIZER SYSTEMS

Klymenko T.,

Candidate of Agricultural Sciences

Petruk V.,

Tashlikovich I.,

Tsvirkun D.,

Oksentyuk Y.,

Shevchuk V.,

Kuchma Y.

applicants of higher education OS master

Polissia National University

Zhytomyr, Ukraine

ABSTRACT

The results of determining the leaf surface area of a potato plant under different fertilization systems are presented. With the introduction of mineral fertilizers in accordance with the biological characteristics of the varieties and the agrochemical characteristics of the soil, it is possible to fully provide potatoes with nutrients in the required ratio and thus contribute to the formation of a high yield of tubers.

Keywords: potato, leaf surface area, fertilizer, manure, siderates.

Formulation of the problem. Potatoes are a valuable agricultural crop and are used in many areas of human activity. It is an indispensable food product, it is widely used for feeding animals and as a raw material for obtaining various potato products, starch, and alcohol [5].

Potatoes are sensitive to changes in soil and air temperature and, as a light-loving culture, react noticeably to a lack of light and are demanding on the water regime. In addition, it is a good precursor for various agricultural crops [3].

Increasing the yield and quality of potato tubers is directly related to biochemical reactions and the accumulation of carbohydrates in plants. Synthesis of carbohydrates (starch) through plant photosynthesis is a system of complex biochemical reactions that significantly depend on the leaf surface area of potato plants [4].

It is known that the optimal plant lighting conditions for photosynthesis are if the total leaf surface is approximately 3-4 times or more greater than the soil area and is at least 35-40 thousand m² /ha [5].

To obtain a high and high-quality harvest, it is necessary to apply a sufficient amount of fertilizers. It makes sense to apply mineral fertilizer for potatoes in several stages. In the fall, during plowing, nitroamphoska and potassium sulfate are applied under the potatoes. It is also possible to fertilize potatoes with urea [1]. In the spring, immediately before planting, we will apply nitrophosk and nitrogen sulfate.

It is better to apply additional potash fertilizers to potatoes in the spring after soil analysis. When planting, we use NPK liquid fertilizers for potatoes. The application rate is determined by the planned harvest [5].

Given the decrease in manure production in the farms of the Polissia zone and the high cost of mineral fertilizers when growing potatoes, it is not possible to apply their recommended rates. This requires the search for alternative sources of organic mass entering the soil, which would contribute to obtaining high yields by increasing the index of the leaf surface area and the net

productivity of plants [2]. At the same time, a special place belongs to the use of straw and siderates when growing potatoes.

The most common, traditionally used ones are, of course, half-rotted manure; introduction of post-harvest stand post-harvest sowing of green manure crops (primarily legumes); use of post-harvest residues of cereals, legumes and industrial crops; use of perennial cereal and leguminous grasses in crop rotations [3].

One of the new and promising areas of potato growing is the use of biological fertilizers and plant protection products. Such drugs are quite effective, increasing the yield and quality of tubers, and do not harm the environment [6].

Tasks of research. The purpose of the research was to study changes in the leaf surface area index of potato plants depending on the species and fertilization rates.

Research objects and methods. The object of research was the leaf surface area of potato plants, organic and mineral fertilizers.

The research was carried out in a stationary field experiment at the experimental field of the Polish National University.

The soil is a light-gray gilded sandy loam on loess-like loam. The soil layer of 0-20 cm is characterized by the following agrochemical parameters: humus content is 1,3%, the reaction of the soil solution is moderately acidic, the amount of absorbed bases and the degree of soil saturation with bases are low and are, respectively, 1,80-2,07 mg-eq./100g of soil and 46,5-53,2%, the content of mobile forms of nitrogen and phosphorus is average, potassium is low.

The following fertilizer was used:

1. By-products of winter rye - straw (3 t/ha)
2. Sideral fertilizer - oil radish (12 t/ha)
3. Dung
4. Mineral fertilizer

Variants of potato fertilization:

1. Control (without fertilizers)
2. Siderates + straw (+ N₁₀ per 1 ton of straw)

3. N₅₀P₄₀K₇₀

4. Manure 25 t/ha + N₂₅P₂₀K₃₅

5. Manure 37,5 t/ha + N_{12,5}P₁₀K_{17,5}

The main cultivation of the soil for potatoes was based on cultivation without rotation of the scyba.

The cutting method was used to determine the leaf surface area.

Method of vysichok. Sheets from the sample were weighed to the second decimal place, punches were made with a special key of a certain diameter. Knowing the mass and area of the cuttings, as well as the total mass of the leaf, the area of the leaf was determined by the formula: $S = M \cdot S_1 / M_1 \text{ cm}^2$, where M is the total mass of the leaf, g, S₁ is the area of one cutout, cm²; M₁ – mass of cuttings, g [6].

The area of the leaf surface was determined according to the standard method. Potato growing technology is generally accepted for the Polissia zone.

Statistical processing of the experimental material was carried out according to the methodology using the MS Excel program.

Research results. As a result of the conducted research, it was established that the formation of the leaf surface of plants depended significantly on the type and rates of fertilization (Table 1).

Intensive increase in leaf area occurred in the intervals from germination to flowering of plants, where they reached their maximum size. If the leaf surface area index was 0,4-1,8 in the phase of full growth, then this indicator increased to 2,3-6,8 units in the flowering phase.

At the beginning of the natural death of the tops, the area of the leaf surface decreased compared to the flowering phase, where the area index was 1,8-5,4, which is associated with the death of the leaves of the lower tier.

Table 1.

Potato leaf surface area index depending on the type and fertilizer rate

Fertilizer options	Phases of plant development					
	Full stairs		Flowering		Natural death of the tops	
	Index	%	Index	%	Index	%
1. Control (without fertilizers)	0,4	100	2,3	100	1,8	100
2. Siderates + straw	1,0	301	4,7	190	3,6	187
3. N ₅₀ P ₄₀ K ₇₀	1,4	435	5,4	220	4,5	232
4. Manure 25 t/ha + N ₂₅ P ₂₀ K ₃₅	1,4	435	5,8	234	4,5	235
5. Manure 37,5 t/ha + N _{12,5} P ₁₀ K _{17,5}	1,8	536	6,9	280	5,4	272
NIR _{0,5} , units	0,3		0,4		0,5	

The increase in the formation of the leaf surface area was influenced by the types and rates of fertilizers. Thus, the introduction of straw and siderates contributed to an increase in the area of leaves in the flowering phase. If in the control (without fertilizers) the index was 2,2, then in the fertilized version – 4,7. Applying only mineral fertilizers (option 3) increased the leaf area by 2 times compared to the control. In the flowering phase, a significant increase in the leaf surface area was observed with the combined application of manure 25 t/ha and mineral fertilizers N₂₅P₂₀K₃₅, where the index of the leaf surface area was 5,8 units compared to 2,3 in the control (without fertilizers), that is, the area was larger by 2,4 times.

The largest leaf surface area during the growing season was formed by plants with the combined application of manure 37,5 t/ha and mineral fertilizers N_{12,5}P₁₀K_{17,5}, in the flowering phase, the index of the leaf area was 6,9, and in the withering phase of the top, in this variant, the index decreased to 5,4 units.

That is, fertilizers significantly influenced the rate of formation of the assimilation apparatus and the size of the active leaf surface of plants, which made it possible to increase the yield of potatoes.

Research results show that providing potatoes with the main nutrients through fertilizers allows to significantly increase the area of the assimilation apparatus, namely, to increase plant productivity and, due to this, to obtain a significant increase in yield.

Conclusions. Due to the shortage of organic and mineral fertilizers when growing potatoes, it is recommended to use straw in combination with siderates,

which will ensure the production of ecologically safe products, manure and moderate rates of mineral fertilizers, which increases the size of the active leaf surface of plants, the synthesis of carbohydrates and obtaining a high yield of tubers potatoes.

References

- Balashova G. S., Yuzyuk S. M. Potato crop formation in southern Ukraine under drip irrigation. Irrigated agriculture. Kherson, 2016. Vol. 66. P. 124-127.
- Biological features of potatoes. Electronic encyclopedia of agriculture. URL: <http://www.AgroScience.com.ua>. 2008–2009.
- Management of agricultural service cooperatives: a practical guide / S.M. Prylipko et al. Cherkasy: O.Yu. Vovchok Publisher, 2017. 200 p.
- Nalobina O.O., Shimko A.V. Analysis of the development of the potato industry and review of potato harvesting equipment. Agricultural machines: collection of science and technology. Lutsk: LNTU, 2015. Issue No. 31. P.106-113.
- Klymenko T. V., Radko V. G., Trembitska O. I., Zhuravel S. V. Growing potatoes in short-rotation crop rotations: monograph. Zhytomyr: ZhNAEU, 2018. 138 c.
- Methodical recommendations for conducting research with potatoes / edited by V. V. Kononchenko. - Nemishaev: IC of the Ukrainian Academy of Sciences, 2002. - 183 p.